

Low-Complexity Tensor-Based Monostatic Sensing for IRS-Assisted Communication Systems

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Abstract—This paper proposes a tensor-based parameter estimation algorithm for sensing in an intelligent reflecting surface-assisted system. We present a higher-order singular value decomposition-based solution that exploits the tensor structure of the received echo signal to jointly estimate the target’s delay, Doppler, and angular information. Our tensor-based solution can estimate the parameters individually at low complexity, benefiting from parallel computation. Complexity analysis is carried out in comparison with a baseline scheme that does not exploit the intrinsic multilinear structure of the sensed signal. Simulation results show that our proposed tensor-based method can achieve the same performance as the reference method while drastically reducing the computational complexity.

Index Terms—Intelligent reflecting surfaces, tensor-based sensing, higher-order singular value decomposition, monostatic sensing, complexity analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the intelligent reflecting surfaces (IRSs) implementation has been vastly researched due to its promising capabilities of improving the overall system throughput, which has the potential to enable the desirable standards of the sixth generation (6G) of mobile communications [1]–[3]. The IRS is a two-dimensional planar object composed of a high number of passive reflecting elements capable of individually changing the phase shifts of impinging electromagnetic waves to smartly maximize the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at some intended receiver [4].

In this context, radar sensing and communication systems are advancing towards elevated frequency bands, increasing the number of antennas that allow miniaturization (smaller size arrays) and signal processing. This convergence presents a compelling prospect for integrating sensing functionalities into wireless infrastructures in future networks. Although this functionality integration has been investigated under different names over the past decades, it has only caught the attention of academia and industry in the past couple of years. This radar sensing and communication integration is commonly known as integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) [5], [6]. Here, by ISAC, the objective is to share the spectrum

more efficiently and/or reuse the existing wireless network infrastructure for sensing. Based on this concept, the IRS arises as an interesting tool for ISAC systems due to its capability of smartly reshaping the propagation environment to enhance system metrics and also illuminating non-line of sight (NLOS) areas. In this work, we utilize the IRSs to enhance the sensing aspects of the network while employing a communications waveform to sense the channel characteristics. Also, due to the passive essence of the IRS, any sensing procedure must be implemented at the end nodes of the network by using the received echo signal reflected by the IRS. Several works have already addressed this problem, as the ones mentioned in [7]–[11]

In the work of [7], the IRS is employed as a means to improve the detection performance of a multi-target multiple input multiple output (MIMO) radar system while jointly optimizing the radar waveform and the IRS phase-shift. The authors in [8] consider that the IRS is deployed to increase the spatial diversity of a radar system by creating an additional virtual line of sight (LOS) path between the radar and the intended target. In [9], the authors investigate an IRS-assisted NLOS sensing scenario and propose the active and passive beamforming design that minimizes the Cramér-Rao lower bound (CRLB). The work [10] proposes a secure sensing scenario with a target-mounted IRS that aims to enhance the sensing performance of the overall system while preventing detection of the target by potential eavesdroppers. The authors in [11] propose a parameter estimation method based on the design of a generalized likelihood ratio test (GLRT) detector, which involves the computation of a four-dimensional parameter peak search of delay-Doppler-azimuth-elevation. To simplify the computation, the authors employ a repetitive IRS phase-shift profile that breaks the four-dimensional search into a delay-Doppler and azimuth-elevation search problems.

In this paper, we develop low-complexity monostatic sensing-based methods in IRS-assisted networks. Notably, we propose a reinterpretation of the monostatic sensing IRS-assisted scenario proposed in [11]. The solution of this paper resorts to tensor methods to recast the received echo signal at the base station (BS) as a third-order rank-one tensor from which we solve the parameter estimation problem by employing the well-known higher-order singular value decomposition (HOSVD) algorithm. We perform a complexity analysis of the proposed scheme and study the effect of different parameters on the performance of IRS-assisted ISAC networks. Our simulation results show that the proposed tensor-based sensing solution performs similarly to the benchmark solution of [11] in terms of root mean squared error (RMSE) while substantially reducing the computational

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Fig. 1: IRS-assisted SISO Monostatic Sensing.

complexity to solve the parameter estimation problem.

Notation: Scalars, vectors, matrices, and tensors are represented as a , \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{A} , and \mathcal{A} . Also, \mathbf{A}^* , \mathbf{A}^T , \mathbf{A}^H , and \mathbf{A}^\dagger stand for the conjugate, transpose, Hermitian, and pseudo-inverse, of a matrix \mathbf{A} . The j th column of $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times J}$ is denoted by $\mathbf{A}_j \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times 1}$. The operator $\text{D}(\cdot)$ converts a vector into a diagonal matrix, $\text{D}_j(\mathbf{B})$ forms a diagonal matrix $R \times R$ out of the j th row of $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{J \times R}$. Also, \mathbf{I}_N denotes an identity matrix of size $N \times N$. The symbols \otimes , \diamond , and \odot indicate the Kronecker, Khatri-Rao, and Hadamard products.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Our system model revisits the scenario proposed in [11]. Specifically, we consider a downlink monostatic¹ IRS-aided scenario under LOS blockage with a dual-functional BS with a single antenna dedicated to transmit an orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) waveform and receives the echo signal backscattered by the target through the IRS. We consider a passive IRS equipped with N reflecting elements. Furthermore, the IRS localization and orientation are assumed to be known, which is an acceptable assumption given that, in practice, the IRS has a fixed position. The BS transmits an OFDM signal with N_c subcarriers and M symbols, with $x_{n_c, m}$ denoting the complex data/pilot on the n_c th subcarrier of the m th symbol. Assuming the existence of a single target, the received OFDM echo signal at the BS, switching to frequency-domain, is expressed as [11]

$$y_{n_c, m} = \alpha \underbrace{\mathbf{a}^T(\phi) \text{D}(\mathbf{w}_m) \mathbf{p}(\theta)}_{\text{Target-IRS-BS path}} \underbrace{\mathbf{p}^T(\theta) \text{D}(\mathbf{w}_m) \mathbf{a}(\phi)}_{\text{BS-IRS-Target path}} \times [\mathbf{c}(\tau)]_{n_c} [\mathbf{d}(\nu)]_m x_{n_c, m} + z_{n_c, m}, \quad (1)$$

where $\phi = [\phi_{az}, \phi_{el}]^T$ is the angle of arrival (AoA) from the BS to the IRS, $\theta = [\theta_{az}, \theta_{el}]^T$ is the angle of departure (AoD) from the IRS to the target, and $\mathbf{a}(\phi) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{p}(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ are the two-dimensional steering vectors expressed as [12]

$$\mathbf{a}(\phi) = \mathbf{a}(\phi_{az}, \phi_{el}) \otimes \mathbf{a}(\phi_{el}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{p}(\theta) = \mathbf{p}(\theta_{az}, \theta_{el}) \otimes \mathbf{p}(\theta_{el}) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}, \quad (3)$$

¹In a monostatic sensing scenario, the self-interference is a natural issue present [5]. In this work, the self-interference is out of scope as for the baseline state-of-the-art competitor [11], since we aim to provide a lower complexity solution for the problem of [11].

with ϕ_{az} and ϕ_{el} being the azimuth and elevation AoA, and θ_{az} and θ_{el} being the azimuth and elevation AoD, respectively. Also, $\mathbf{w}_m \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the IRS phase-shift profile for the m th OFDM symbol defined as $\mathbf{w}_m = [e^{j\zeta_{1,m}}, \dots, e^{j\zeta_{N,m}}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$, where $\zeta_{n,m}$ is the phase-shift of the n th IRS element at the m th OFDM symbol. The frequency-domain steering vector as a function of the delay τ is given by $\mathbf{c}(\tau) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times 1}$ and the element linked to the n th OFDM subcarrier is $[\mathbf{c}(\tau)]_{n_c} \in \mathbb{C}$. Also, $\mathbf{d}(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the time-domain steering vector as function of the Doppler ν and the element linked to the m th OFDM symbol is $[\mathbf{d}(\nu)]_m \in \mathbb{C}$, and $z_{n_c, m} \in \mathbb{C}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) component at the n th subcarrier of the m th symbol. Finally, the magnitude of the complex gain, $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$, is given by

$$|\alpha| = \sqrt{\frac{P_t G_1^2 G_2^2 F_1^2(\phi_{el}) F_2^2(\theta_{el}) d_x^2 d_y^2 \lambda^2 \sigma_{\text{RCS}}}{(4\pi)^5 d_1^4 d_2^4}}, \quad (4)$$

where P_t is the transmit power, G_1 is the BS transmit antenna gain, G_2 is the BS receive antenna gain, $F_1^2(\phi_{el})$ is the normalized IRS power radiation pattern at the AoA ϕ_{el} , $F_2^2(\theta_{el})$ is the normalized IRS power radiation pattern at the AoD θ_{el} , d_x and d_y denotes the IRS spacing along the horizontal and vertical domains, respectively, λ is the carrier wavelength, σ_{RCS} is the target radar cross section (RCS), and d_1 and d_2 denotes the distances BS-IRS and IRS-target, respectively. To compact Equation (1), we can define $\mathbf{b}(\phi, \theta) = \mathbf{a}(\phi) \odot \mathbf{p}(\theta)$ and recast the expression of the echo signal as

$$y_{n_c, m} = \alpha (\mathbf{b}^T(\phi, \theta) \mathbf{w}_m)^2 [\mathbf{c}(\tau)]_{n_c} [\mathbf{d}(\nu)]_m x_{n_c, m} + z_{n_c, m}. \quad (5)$$

To stack over N_c subcarriers and M symbols, we define $\mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ as a matrix that collects the IRS phase-shift patterns during M OFDM symbols. We can recast the received signal in Equation (5) as²

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathbf{X} \odot \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\phi, \theta) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\phi, \theta) \mathbf{W}) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times M}, \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{c}(\tau) \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times 1}$ is the complete frequency-domain steering vector as a function of the delay τ , $\mathbf{d}(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the time-domain steering vector as a function of the Doppler ν , $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times M}$ is the transmitted symbols matrix by the BS where $\mathbf{X}_{n_c, m} = x_{n_c, m}$, and $\mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times M} \sim \mathcal{CN}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma^2 \mathbf{I})$ is the AWGN matrix. Also, by considering that the entries of symbols matrix \mathbf{X} are composed of unitary elements and that the knowledge of the angular information of the channel between the BS and IRS, ϕ , is known at the receiver, then it is possible to simplify the formulation of the received echo signal at the BS with the following expression [11]

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha \mathbf{c}(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\theta) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\theta) \mathbf{W}) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times M}. \quad (7)$$

III. PROPOSED TENSOR-BASED SENSING RECEIVER

This section presents our proposed tensor-based method for parameter estimation and investigates its implementation

²The design of the phase-shift matrix is discussed in Section III A.

Fig. 2: Time-domain protocol of the proposed IRS design.

complexity. Different from [11], our proposed solution recast the received echo signal from the BS-IRS-target-IRS-BS link as a third-order rank-one tensor to solve the parameter estimation problem based on the state-of-the-art HOSVD, as shown in Algorithm 1. The main idea is to exploit the intrinsic multilinear structure of the received signal to estimate the best rank-one approximation of the tensor signal so that in the sequence, we can solve three individual peak search problems from which we obtain the estimates of τ , ν , and θ as shown in Fig. 4. Due to the tensor approach, we harvest considerable complexity gain as shown in Table I.

A. Formulation of the Proposed Tensor Model

From Equation (5), we observe that the IRS pattern is varying with each OFDM symbol period, which results in a coupling between the Doppler ν and the angles (ϕ, θ) as showcased in Equation (7). To solve this, we employ a repetition-based IRS phase-shift pattern to decouple the angular and Doppler parameter estimates, as proposed by [11]. The idea consists of repeating the same phase-shift pattern during a block of Q OFDM symbols while varying this pattern across L blocks, yielding a total time window of $M = QL$ OFDM symbols. This protocol is illustrated in Fig. 2. As a result, the IRS phase shift matrix can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{W} = [\mathbf{w}_1 \cdots \mathbf{w}_L] \otimes \mathbf{1}_Q^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times QL}. \quad (8)$$

Since the angular parameters are not dependent on the time domain, in contrast to the Doppler parameter, such a repetition protocol allows decoupling the estimate of the pure Doppler-related vector from the angle-Doppler-related vector, as will be shown in this section. To exploit this new design for the IRS phase-shift matrix in Equation (7), let us define

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\theta) = \mathbf{b}^T(\theta) \mathbf{W} \odot \mathbf{b}^T(\theta) \mathbf{W} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times QL}, \quad (9)$$

recasting Equation (7) as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha c(\tau) (\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot \mathbf{g}^T(\theta)) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times QL}, \quad (10)$$

and by exploiting the repetitive structure of the IRS phase-shift matrix in Equation (8), it is possible to reformulate $\mathbf{g}(\theta)$ as

$$\mathbf{g}^T(\theta) = \underbrace{(\mathbf{b}^T(\theta) [\mathbf{w}_1 \cdots \mathbf{w}_L])^2}_{\mathbf{g}_L^T(\theta) \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times L}} \otimes \mathbf{1}_Q^T, \quad (11)$$

and plugging Equation (11) into Equation (10) leads to

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha c(\tau) [\mathbf{d}^T(\nu) \odot (\mathbf{g}_L^T(\theta) \otimes \mathbf{1}_Q^T)] + \mathbf{Z}. \quad (12)$$

Fig. 3: Noiseless received sensing signal tensor.

By defining $\mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ as

$$\mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) = [1, e^{j2\pi\nu T_s}, \dots, e^{j2\pi\nu(Q-1)T_s}] \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times 1}, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{d}_L(\nu) = [1, e^{j2\pi\nu Q T_s}, \dots, e^{j2\pi\nu Q(L-1)T_s}] \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}, \quad (14)$$

allows us to express the time-domain steering vector as a function of the Doppler as $\mathbf{d}(\nu) = \mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu)$. Plugging this expression into Equation (12) yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = \alpha c(\tau) [(\mathbf{d}_L^T(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q^T(\nu)) \odot (\mathbf{g}_L^T(\theta) \otimes \mathbf{1}_Q^T)] + \mathbf{Z},$$

and taking its transpose and applying property $(\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{c}) \odot (\mathbf{b} \otimes \mathbf{d}) = (\mathbf{a} \odot \mathbf{b}) \otimes (\mathbf{c} \odot \mathbf{d})$, leads to the following expression

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= \alpha c(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\theta) \otimes \mathbf{1}_Q) \odot (\mathbf{d}_L(\nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu))]^T + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha c(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\theta) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu)) \otimes (\mathbf{1}_Q \odot \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu))]^T + \mathbf{Z}, \\ &= \alpha c(\tau) [(\mathbf{g}_L(\theta) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu)) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu)]^T + \mathbf{Z}. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Defining $\beta(\theta, \nu) = \alpha (\mathbf{g}_L(\theta) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\nu)) \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times 1}$ and plugging it into Equation (15) yields

$$\mathbf{Y} = c(\tau) (\beta(\theta, \nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu))^T + \mathbf{Z}, \quad (16)$$

which can be viewed as the first-mode unfolding of the following rank-one third-order tensor \mathcal{Y}

$$\mathcal{Y} = c(\tau) \circ \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) \circ \beta(\theta, \nu) + \mathbf{Z} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times Q \times L} \quad (17)$$

with its matrix unfoldings being written as [13]

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(1)} = c(\tau) (\beta(\theta, \nu) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu))^T \in \mathbb{C}^{N_c \times QL}, \quad (18)$$

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(2)} = \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) (\beta(\theta, \nu) \otimes c(\tau))^T \in \mathbb{C}^{Q \times N_c L}, \quad (19)$$

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(3)} = \beta(\theta, \nu) (\mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) \otimes c(\tau))^T \in \mathbb{C}^{L \times N_c Q}. \quad (20)$$

An illustration of the received sensing tensor (in the noiseless case) is shown in Figure 3.

B. HOSVD-based Estimation

Estimating the factors of the tensor in Equation (17) requires us to find a multi-linear approximation of \mathcal{Y} . This can be achieved by employing the state-of-the-art truncated HOSVD algorithm [13]–[15]. Let us define the following tensor minimization problem

$$\arg \min_{c(\tau), \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu), \beta(\theta, \nu)} \|\mathcal{Y} - c(\tau) \circ \mathbf{d}_Q(\nu) \circ \beta(\theta, \nu)\|_F^2. \quad (21)$$

Fig. 4: Block diagram of the proposed parameter estimation

The optimization problem in Equation (21) is solved by means of the HOSVD, by computing multiple singular value decompositions (SVDs) for each unfolding of \mathcal{Y} , as follows

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(1)} = \mathbf{U}^{(1)} \Sigma^{(1)} \mathbf{V}^{(1)H}, \quad (22)$$

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(2)} = \mathbf{U}^{(2)} \Sigma^{(2)} \mathbf{V}^{(2)H}, \quad (23)$$

$$[\mathcal{Y}]_{(3)} = \mathbf{U}^{(3)} \Sigma^{(3)} \mathbf{V}^{(3)H}. \quad (24)$$

and the estimates of $\mathbf{c}(\tau)$, $\mathbf{d}_Q(\nu)$, and $\beta(\theta, \nu)$ are built from the dominant left singular vectors of $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(1)}$, $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(2)}$, and $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(3)}$, respectively, i.e.,

$$\hat{\mathbf{c}}(\tau) = \mathbf{U}_{\cdot 1}^{(1)}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{d}}_Q(\nu) = \mathbf{U}_{\cdot 1}^{(2)}, \quad \hat{\beta}(\theta, \nu) = \mathbf{U}_{\cdot 1}^{(3)}. \quad (25)$$

After the HOSVD stage, we employ a one-dimensional peak search from $\hat{\mathbf{c}}(\tau)$ to estimate the delay τ , a one-dimensional peak search from $\hat{\mathbf{d}}_Q(\nu)$ to estimate the Doppler ν , and finally a peak search from $\hat{\beta}(\theta, \nu)$ to estimate the angular information between the IRS and the target, θ . Since the received echo signal follows a rank-one tensor model, the HOSVD leads to unique estimates up to a trivial scaling factor affecting each estimated vector. Note that the peak search problem is insensitive to such a scaling factor. Starting by τ and ν , we solve the following peak search problems to obtain an estimation of delay and Doppler

$$\hat{\tau} = \arg \max_{\tau} \frac{|\mathbf{c}^H(\tau) \hat{\mathbf{c}}(\tau)|^2}{|\hat{\mathbf{c}}(\tau)|^2}, \quad \hat{\nu} = \arg \max_{\nu} \frac{|\mathbf{d}_Q^H(\nu) \hat{\mathbf{d}}_Q(\nu)|^2}{|\hat{\mathbf{d}}_Q(\nu)|^2}. \quad (26)$$

Before solving the last peak search problem that estimates the angular information, we exploit knowledge of the Doppler estimated in Equation (26) to simplify the three-dimensional search in $\beta(\theta, \nu)$ to a two-dimensional search in $\mathbf{g}_L(\theta)$. To obtain an estimation of $\mathbf{g}_L(\theta)$ from $\hat{\beta}(\theta, \nu)$ we rewrite

$$\mathbf{g}_L(\hat{\theta}) = \hat{\beta}(\theta, \nu) \odot (\mathbf{d}_L(\hat{\nu}))^{-1}, \quad (27)$$

and with the knowledge of the delay estimated in Equation (26), we formulate the following cost function [11]

$$\hat{\theta} = \arg \max_{\theta} \frac{|\mathbf{c}^H(\hat{\tau}) [\mathcal{Y}]_{(1)} [(\hat{\mathbf{g}}_L(\theta) \odot \mathbf{d}_L(\hat{\nu})) \otimes \mathbf{d}_Q(\hat{\nu})]^*|^2}{|\hat{\mathbf{g}}_L(\theta)|^2}. \quad (28)$$

Algorithm 1 HOSVD-based parameter estimation

Require: Tensor \mathcal{Y}

- 1: Define the SVDs of $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(1)}$, $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(2)}$, and $[\mathcal{Y}]_{(3)}$ with (22)-(24).
 - 2: Compute the estimation of $\mathbf{c}(\tau)$, $\mathbf{d}_Q(\nu)$, and $\beta(\theta, \nu)$ with (25).
 - 3: Compute the estimation of τ and ν with (26)
 - 4: Compute the estimation of $\mathbf{g}_L(\theta)$ with (27)
 - 5: Compute the estimation of θ with (28)
 - 6: **return** $\hat{\tau}$, $\hat{\nu}$, and $\hat{\theta}$
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C. Complexity Analysis

In Table I, we derive the approximated computational complexity in terms of $\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$ for the selected baseline algorithm from [11], and our proposed solution summarized in Alg. 1. The baseline proposed by the authors of [11] solves two peak search problems, one to jointly estimate τ and ν and the other to estimate the azimuth and elevation components of θ . Regarding our proposed algorithm, the HOSVD-based parameter estimation of Equation (21) computes three rank-one SVDs followed by three peak search problems derived in Equation (26). We consider that $\mathcal{O}(N_1 N_2)$ is the complexity associated with the rank-one approximation of a matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_1 \times N_2}$ by the SVD [16]. Also, the complexity associated with the computation of the inner product between two vectors $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_1 \times 1}$ and $\mathbf{b} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_2 \times 1}$ and the product between a vector $\mathbf{a} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_1 \times 1}$ and a matrix $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_1 \times N_2}$ is given by $(2N_1 - 1)$ and $(2N_1 N_2 - N_2)$, respectively [17]. We use these definitions to compute the approximate number of flops linked to each iteration needed to solve the peak search problems of both the baseline [11] and the proposed Alg. 1 considering that R_τ , R_ν , and R_θ are the number of points of each grid defined by the peak search problems of τ , ν , and θ , respectively. The baseline [11] complexity consists of solving the two-dimensional peak search problems that estimate τ and ν , and the θ . Meanwhile the complexity of the proposed solution in Alg. 1 consists of solving the tensor estimation in Equation 21 employing the HOSVD followed by two one-dimensional peak search problems, Equation (26), and a single two-dimensional peak search problem in Equation (28). From Table I, we can observe that the proposed Alg. 1 has a lower complexity when compared to the baseline [11] since it can solve the peak search problem of τ and ν in parallel.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

We evaluate the performance of the proposed tensor-based algorithm by comparing it with the parameter estimation method on [11] in terms of both RMSE and computational complexity. We design the IRS phase-shift matrix \mathbf{W} as a truncated discrete Fourier transform (DFT) of size N with L columns. The IRS elevation and azimuth angles of arrival, ϕ , and departure, θ , are randomly generated from a uniform distribution between $[0, \pi/2]$. The parameter estimation accuracy is evaluated in terms of the RMSE given by $\text{RMSE}(x) = \sqrt{\mathbb{E} \left[|x^{(m)} - \hat{x}^{(m)}|^2 / |x^{(m)}|^2 \right]}$ with x being one of the estimated parameters at the m th experiment, with $V = 5 \times 10^3$ being the number of channel realizations. Also,

TABLE I: Computational complexity of the baseline and the proposed algorithms

Algorithm	Computational Complexity
Baseline [11]	$\mathcal{O}(R_\tau R_\nu L(2N_c Q + N_c - 1) + R_\theta(2N_c Q + N_c - 1))$
Proposed	$\mathcal{O}(\underbrace{3N_c QL}_{\text{HOSVD in 21}} + \underbrace{R_\tau(2N_c - 1)}_{\text{Equation 26}} + \underbrace{R_\nu(2QL - 1)}_{\text{Equation 26}} + \underbrace{R_\theta(2N_c Q + N_c - 1)}_{\text{Equation 28}})$

the SNR is defined as $\text{SNR} = \|\mathbf{Y}\|_{\text{F}}^2 / \|\mathbf{Z}\|_{\text{F}}^2$ with $\sigma_{\mathbf{Z}}^2$ being the noise variance. Table II summarizes the remaining simulation parameters. In Fig. 5, we evaluate the RMSE performance of delay estimation for the baseline algorithm in [11] and the proposed Algorithm 1 for two different scenarios, $Q = 4$ and $Q = 8$. The baseline solution performs slightly better in the very low SNR range. Note that the performance of both methods is the same at SNR levels higher than -5 dB. It can also be seen that the delay estimation performance of both methods is not influenced by the block size Q .

Similarly, in Fig. 6 we evaluate the RMSE performance of Doppler estimation for the baseline algorithm in [11] and the proposed Algorithm 1 for the two same scenarios, $Q = 4$ and $Q = 8$. The proposed solution performs similarly to the baseline for most of the considered SNR range while exhibiting some performance degradation for very low SNR levels. Indeed, the proposed method, although much simpler than the one of [11], is a bit more sensitive to very high noise. We can also note that increasing the block size Q (or, equivalently, the repetition factor of the IRS phase shifts) improves performance for both methods.

In Fig. 7 we observe the angular estimation RMSE performance for the baseline algorithm in [11] and the proposed tensor-based sensing algorithm for the scenarios $Q = 4$ and $Q = 8$. In this case, both the baseline in [11] and the proposed solution have the same performance for both scenarios, while the increase in Q harms the estimation for both methods. Note that both the proposed and the baseline methods extract the angular estimates using a maximum likelihood criterion (see equation 28), which explains their similar performances. Note, however, that the proposed method has an overall lower complexity due to the decoupling of the delay and Doppler estimates achieved after the HOSVD stage.

In Fig. 8, we show the computational complexity curves for the proposed solution in Algorithm 1 and the baseline solution in [11] as a function of the number of subcarriers. The other parameters are fixed according to Table II. The baseline method is approximately 10 times more complex than the proposed tensor-based method, while the complexity increases linearly with the number of subcarriers. This behavior is explained by analyzing Table I. The complexity of the reference method is dependent on the product $R_\tau R_\nu$, which corresponds to the size of the grids defined by the peak search problems that estimate the delay and the Doppler since there is a coupling estimate of the delay and the Doppler in [11]. However, Algorithm 1 can estimate the delay and the Doppler in parallel, which breaks the product $R_\tau R_\nu$ into a summation. Similarly, in Fig. 9, we plot the complexity curve according

Fig. 5: Delay estimation performance of the proposed solution and the baseline algorithm in [11].

Fig. 6: Doppler estimation performance of the proposed solution and the baseline algorithm in [11].

to Table I as a function of the number of points in each grid that solves the peak search problems. These results indicate that the proposed tensor solution is approximately 10 times less complex than the competing method [11] for a varying number of subcarriers.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper focuses on the parameter estimation problem in a monostatic sensing system assisted by IRS. It proposes a tensor-based estimation algorithm, summarized in Alg. 1, that estimates the delay, Doppler, and angles in an IRS-assisted scenario. The proposed solution in Alg. 1 performs slightly worse for delay and Doppler estimation at medium SNR, while at high and low SNR, both algorithms show similar performance. Regarding the AoA estimation, the baseline solution in [11] and the proposed tensor-based method achieve the same performance in terms of RMSE.

TABLE II: Simulation parameters.

IRS size	$N_x N_y = 4 \times 4 = 16$
IRS spacing	$d_x = d_y = \lambda/2$
AoA generation	$\{\phi_{az}, \phi_{el}\} \sim U(0, 90^\circ)$
AoD generation	$\{\theta_{az}, \theta_{el}\} \sim U(0, 90^\circ)$
Wavelength	1.07×10^{-2} m
Carrier frequency	28 GHz
Subcarrier spacing Δf	120 KHz
Symbol duration	$1/\Delta f$
Channel realizations	5000
Number of symbols	64
Number of subcarriers	16
Distance BS - IRS	10 m
Distance IRS - target	5 m
Radar cross section (RCS)	2m^2
Grid size for (26)	$R_\tau = R_\nu = 100$
Grid size for (28)	$R_\theta = 10000$

Fig. 7: Angle estimation performance of the proposed solution and the baseline algorithm in [11].

Fig. 8: Computational complexity comparison as a function of the number of subcarriers.

However, the proposed solution substantially reduces the computational complexity and improves scalability: with increasing subcarriers, our solution is 10 times less complex than the baseline algorithm. As a perspective, we will investigate the performance of the proposed tensor-based solution by considering the intrinsic self-interference of monostatic sensing scenarios.

Fig. 9: Computational complexity comparison as a function of the number of grid points.

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